

Soil organic carbon and clay prediction and mapping using EnMAP data: a sensor- and domain-based performance comparison

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Abstract

Soil organic carbon (SOC) and clay are vital parameters required by the soil living organisms for their health and ecosystem performance. Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program (EnMAP) hyperspectral sensor's data was employed in this study for prediction and mapping of SOC and clay in agricultural soils. Results were compared with those obtained from the Landsat 8-OLI (L08-OLI) multispectral and Sentinel-2 (S2) superspectral satellites data. The CASI/SASI (CS) airborne hyperspectral data was also used as the reference. After extraction of the bare soil pixels using normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), normalized burn ratio 2 (NBR2) and normalized cellulose absorption index (nCAI) spectral indices, prediction models were developed on remaining samples using the random forest (RF) algorithm. Comparing the indices' performance, nCAI recognized more bare soil samples-pixels in common between the EnMAP and CS. EnMAP outperformed L08-OLI and S2 in extraction of the bare soil sample-pixels. It shared more sample-pixels in common with CS sensor and ground truth photos taken during the sampling. Furthermore, EnMAP outperformed the other two spaceborne sensors, for both sites separately and together (RPD ≥ 1.35 , $R^2 \geq 0.56$, RMSE $\leq 0.12\%$ for SOC and RPD ≥ 1.55 , $R^2 \geq 0.69$, RMSE $\leq 1.61\%$ for clay) with higher accuracies close to those yielded by CS data. Considering the distribution maps, those created based on EnMAP image presented similar spatial distribution trends with those developed using CS. Overall, in this study, the

EnMAP data showed enough promise, higher than satellite-based L08-OLI and S2 multispectral sensors, for prediction and mapping of SOC and clay in the agricultural topsoil.

Keywords: EnMAP, soil parameters, spaceborne sensors, hyperspectral airborne, bare soil selection, modeling and prediction

1. Introduction

Soil organic carbon (SOC) and clay are two key soil parameters that play important roles in its physical, chemical, and biological functions. SOC mainly affects fertility and the nutrient cycle of the terrestrial ecosystems (Lenka et al., 2020). Clay is the smallest fraction (less than 0.002 mm) of the soil with a significant role in soil's water availability, cation exchange capacity (CEC) and carbon and nutrients storage (Six et al., 2004). Continuous monitoring of these soil properties is hence of great importance, both from the economic and environmental aspects. The laboratory-based chemical and physical analysis provide accurate results. However, they are time and resource consuming, which may usually cost a huge amount of budget for continuous monitoring of SOC and clay. These problems have sparked an increased interest toward cost- and time-effective alternative estimation methods.

As a rapid, cost-effective, and eco-friendly technique, airborne and spaceborne (satellite-based) remote sensing within the spectral range of visible–near infrared–shortwave infrared (Vis–NIR–SWIR; 350–2500 nm), has become an efficient complementary for laboratory-based quantitative measurements of SOC, clay, and several other soil parameters (Gomez et al., 2008; Gholizadeh et al., 2018a; Castaldi et al., 2023). It is based on the spectral response of the soil functional groups to electromagnetic radiation (Gholizadeh et al., 2018b). Vibrations within the chemical bonds of the soil active spectral components lead to that spectral response. The acquired data can then be utilized for prediction of soil parameters, in direct form of primary predictors or as indirect ancillary covariates.

Various multispectral (3 to 7 bands) and superspectral (7 to 20 bands) sensors have been implemented aboard the satellite-, airborne-, or drone-based platforms to study various soil parameters including SOC (Angelopoulou et al., 2019) and clay (Castaldi et al., 2023; Gomez et al., 2018). Of those, the Landsat and Sentinel satellite series offer unprecedented amounts of free multi- and superspectral data for monitoring of the global environment. Sentinel-2 (S2), as example, with average temporal resolution of 5 days, has yielded successful SOC and/or

clay estimations in Africa (Hengl et al., 2021), Americas (Bellinaso et al., 2021; de Almeida Minihoni et al., 2021; Castaldi et al., 2023), Asia (Abdoli et al., 2023; Bao et al., 2023), Europe (Gholizadeh et al., 2018a; Castaldi et al., 2019a; Vaudour et al., 2019), and Oceania (Nguyen et al., 2022; Tran et al., 2024).

The hyperspectral data (with 20 to 500 bands) contain more wavelengths relevant to specific soil parameters, making it more alluring than the lower spectral resolution multi- and superspectral data for non-invasive soil monitoring (Mzid et al., 2022; Khosravi et al., 2024). Nevertheless, the majority of hyperspectral sensors have been mounted on airborne or drone-based platforms. Using these low flying altitude aerial platforms has brought about better spatial resolution data and hence more robust models with higher prediction and mapping results (Gholizadeh et al., 2018b). Despite several advantages, low flying platforms are often restricted by spatial coverage, brief flying longevity, elevated operating costs, limited payload, and flight controlling challenges caused by turbulence and strong winds (Hardin et al., 2010; Biney et al., 2021). In addition, unexpected harsh weather can halt the whole imaging campaign and incur notable expenses. In contrast, spaceborne remote sensing has an immense potential for widespread and persistent monitoring of the terrestrial surface and production of various soil trait maps (Biney et al., 2021). The general shortcomings of the data acquired by the classic spaceborne hyperspectral sensors (e.g., Hyperion), such as low spatial and temporal resolution and low signal to noise ratio (SNR) (Gomez et al., 2008) have been tried to be overcome by the current or forthcoming Earth observation (EO) missions such as PRecursores IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa (PRISMA) (Loizzo et al., 2018), DLR Earth Sensing Imaging Spectrometer (DESI) (Kruz et al., 2019), Earth surface Mineral dust source InvesTigation (EMIT) (Green et al., 2020), Hyperspectral Imager SUite (HISUI) (Matsunaga et al., 2021), Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program (EnMAP) (Storch et al., 2023), Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission for the Environment (CHIME) (Nieke et al. 2018), and Spaceborne Hyperspectral Applicative Land and Ocean Mission (SHALOM) (Feingersh et al., 2015).

The successful launch and commissioning of the EnMAP satellite has provided a unique opportunity for global scale high spectral resolution imaging of the Earth surface. According to Guanter et al. (2015), the acquired data can be used for frequent and consistent hyperspectral measurements of diagnostic variables used for description and analysis of the

Earth surface main processes. The mission has a swath width of 30 km and provides 30 m × 30 m pixels image with 224 bands ranging from 418.2 to 2445.5 nm. Thanks to the satellite tilting potential, the temporal resolution can reach to less than 4 days. EnMAP products can assist in monitoring status of different ecosystems, mostly emphasizing on the terrestrial ones such as soil, agricultural, forest, desert, and urban. These capabilities can make EnMAP a reliable source of data to study soil key properties such as SOC and clay.

A serious issue in studying soil surface properties using spectral sensing is that the soil surface is often covered by green vegetation and crop residue (dry vegetation). This may cause spectral mixing and reduction of the soil signal. Using the unique spectral features of these vegetation covers, some indices have been defined to discriminate them from the bare soil (Xiao and Moody, 2005). The normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) (Rouse et al., 1974) for green vegetation and normalized burn ratio 2 (NBR2) (van Deventer et al., 1997) and cellulose absorption index (CAI) (Daughtry et al., 1996) for dry vegetation have been very demanding for that purpose (Dvoráková et al., 2020; Castaldi, 2021; Mzid et al., 2022; Tian et al., 2023). The latter index is based on a broad absorption feature of the dry vegetation within the range of 2000 to 2200 nm of the SWIR region, which is related to some structural compounds such as lignocellulose (Daughtry et al., 1996). In addition, some researchers have proposed using the normalized form of CAI (nCAI) to achieve higher contrast for detection of dry vegetation (Mzid et al., 2022; Angelopoulou et al., 2023). In the case of the EnMAP data, no application of nCAI has yet been reported.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt aiming to construct and evaluate local scale SOC and clay estimation models on the EnMAP actual reflectance spectra. The developed models using the EnMAP data were then compared with those developed employing the data from Landsat 8-OLI (L08-OLI) and S2 satellites, as well as the CASI and SASI airborne hyperspectral images. The performance of NBR2 and nCAI indices on all sensors' spectra were further compared for discrimination of the bare soil pixels from those covered by dry vegetation. Finally, the SOC and clay spatial distribution maps were produced using the models developed based on each imaging spectra.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The study area consists of two agricultural sites of Jičín and Přestavlky, producing maize, potatoes, cereals and oilseed rape in rural regions of the Czech Republic (Fig. 1). According to the World Reference Base (WRB) of soils (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2014), Jičín mainly comprised of Luvisols, Albic Luvisols, Luvic Chernozems on Pleistocene loess while Přestavlky includes Haplic Stagnosol, Haplic and Stagnic Cambisol, Leptosol as the dominant soil unit on Complex of Proterozoic and Paleozoic rocks (schist, granodiorite) (Zizala et al., 2017). The sites have similar climate conditions with high rates of actual and potential degradation by erosion. The main terrain features of the sites include side valley, plateau, toe-slope and back-slope. Long-term tillage, no conservation, plough depth 25 cm and 5–6 course rotation based on the Norfolk system are considered as the main land management practices in the study area (Gholizadeh et al., 2018).

Fig. 1. a) Study sites in the Czech Republic, and sampling locations (green dots) in b) Jičín and c) Přestavlky.

2.2. Field campaign, samples preparation, and laboratory measurements

For this study, a subset of 118 soil samples were selected from those collected during a sampling campaign held in June 2021. Each sample was collected from the topsoil to the depth

of 20 cm, as a composite within an area of 4 m². Sampling was performed based on the stratified random strategy designed by the conditioned Latin Hypercube Sampling (cLHS). The coordinates of each sampling point were determined using a GeoXM (Trimble Inc., Sunnyvale, California, USA) global positioning system (GPS) with 1 m spatial accuracy. As ground truth, a digital ground vertical photograph was taken at each sampling point.

Samples were then air-dried, grinded, sieved (≤ 2 mm) and mixed before analysis. SOC content (%) of each soil sample was determined using the Walkley–Black method. The pipette method was used for analysis of the clay (particles size < 0.002 mm) content of the samples (ISO 11277:2009).

2.3. Multi- and hyperspectral satellite data pre-processing

The L08-OLI level 1T (L1T) and S2 level-2A (L2A) images were selected and downloaded in a way that their acquisition dates were in October 2023, when the EnMAP level 2A (L2A) scenes were acquired (Table S1). The L08-OLI image was subjected to atmospheric corrections using the fast line-of-sight atmospheric analysis of spectral hypercubes (FLAASH) algorithm (Cooley et al., 2002). The L2A product of S2 is obtained by atmospheric correction of the Level-1C top of atmosphere product to the surface reflectance. The spectra of both imageries were transformed to absorbance by $\log(1/R)$, where R is the reflectance.

The L2A EnMAP products had undergone an automated sequence of pre-processing operations including the radiometric correction to top-of-atmosphere (TOA) radiance (Level-1B), orthorectification and geometric correction of Level-1B data (Level-1C), atmospheric correction of the Level-1C data to the bottom-of-atmosphere (BOA) reflectance (Level-2A), calibration of the instrument and quality control (Storch et al., 2023). To avoid the noise caused by the sensor, the bands with wavelengths between 418.2–450 nm and 2400–2445.5 nm were discarded from the raw spectra and further processing (Fig. 2a). The remaining spectra were then transformed to absorbance. A second-order polynomial Savitzky-Golay (SG) smoothing filter (Savitzky & Golay, 1964) with 11 smoothing points was then applied on the absorbance spectra. In order to remove the baseline offset, the first derivative (FD) transformation was finally applied on the SG smoothed spectra (Fig. 2b). As the final pre-processing step, the 30 m pixels bands of L08-OLI and EnMAP and 20 m-pixel bands of S2 were resampled to 10 m to have satellite data with consistent spatial resolutions, making comparison easier. Details about the satellite data bands can be found in Tables S2 to S4.

Fig. 2. EnMAP a) raw reflectance and b) first derivative pre-processed spectra

2.4. Airborne imaging and data pre-processing

The airborne imaging of the study sites was performed on the third of June 2021, 5 days after the last rain, when the topsoil was relatively dry (Table S1). CASI and SASI (Itres Ltd., Calgary, Canada) sensors placed in Cessna 208B Grand Caravan aircraft were employed to record hyperspectral data within the Vis–NIR (380–1050 nm) and SWIR (950–2450 nm) spectral regions, respectively (Table S4). A ground survey was also carried out on the day of the airborne campaign, current soil moisture was measured by time-domain reflectometry (TDR) equipment.

The pre-processing (radiometric and geometric corrections) was accomplished by the Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences. For complete methodology see Gholizadeh et al. (2018a). Similar to EnMAP, the noisy edges of both spectral ranges were removed which resulted in 56 bands (from 459.12 to 981.98 nm) for CASI and 95 bands (from 987.5 to 2397.5 nm) for SASI sensors. To ensure the pixels compatibility, the CASI data were resampled to the spatial resolution of the SASI sensor (2.5 m). After resampling, remaining bands of both sensors were stacked to form a 162-bands nearly full range Vis–NIR–SWIR hyperspectral data cube called CS. Transformation to absorbance, SG smoothing, and

FD transformation were the final pre-processing steps applied on the CS image spectra, with the same parameters as in case of EnMAP.

2.5. Selection of the bare soil pixels

Bare soil pixels selection is an important step since it affects the quality and quantity of samples employed for the development and evaluation of the SOC and clay estimation models. It is also necessary to determine the proper bare soil pixels that are being used for mapping the spatial distribution of the studied soil parameters. NDVI was calculated for all types of data to mask the green vegetation. To do so, different NDVI threshold values between 0.10 and 0.35, with 0.01 increment were used. Pixels containing dry vegetation were also removed using NBR2. In NBR2, the normalized difference of reflectance values between the two key bands (e.g., B11 and B12 on S2) is close to 0 for the bare soil, while will elevate because of dry vegetation (Castaldi et al., 2018). Different NBR2 thresholds between 0.05 and 0.25, with 0.01 increment were also tested, to mask the dry vegetation pixels and to identify those suitable for modeling and mapping SOC and clay. In addition, nCAI was specifically implemented on the hyperspectral data to discriminate the bare soil pixels from the dry vegetation ones. For calculation of nCAI, the endeavor was to select those bands of CS and EnMAP images with center positions maximally close to the 2030, 2100 and 2210 nm wavelengths defined by Daughtry (2001). Different values between 0.0 and 0.1, with 0.01 increment were tested to reach the optimal nCAI thresholds.

The true color composite (TCC) of the high-resolution aerial/satellite images and ground truth photos were used for visual assessment of the cover types obtained for each of the indices and sensors and defining the optimal threshold values. The indices' mathematical formula and related wavelengths for each of the data types can be seen in Table 1.

2.6. Spectral comparison

Soil properties are not fixed and may change over time due to various factors including precipitation, tillage, fertilization, and irrigation (Liebig et al., 2021). Comparing the performance of models developed on spectral data and samples taken on different dates is, hence, challenging. Facing this challenge, it was decided to compare the spectra of the satellite images with those of the airborne image acquired close to the sampling date. This was done to find out whether there were similarities between different spectra and find out if it was reasonable to compare performance of the models developed on those images. Accordingly,

each of the spectra were visually compared at three representative pixels co-located with the soil samples (hereafter sample-pixels), one for each cover type. The NDVI, NBR2 and nCAI spectral indices were also calculated for the same pixels of different datasets and compared (for nCAI, the comparison was only done between the CS and EnMAP). Furthermore, spectral angle mapper (SAM) (Kruse et al., 1993) approach was implemented on the Vis–NIR and SWIR spectral ranges, separately, to determine the similarity between the satellite and CS images reflectance spectra in sample-pixels. The SAM determines the quantitative similarity of two spectra over a desired wavelength range by measuring the angle (θ) between them (Kruse et al., 1993).

2.7. Modeling methods

The remaining bare soil samples were divided into training (75%) and testing (25%) portions using the Kennard–Stone (KS) algorithm (Kennard and Stone, 1969). The SOC and clay prediction models were developed by applying the 5-fold cross-validation on the training subset. Performance of the constructed models was then evaluated on the testing dataset. Each sample contained multi-, super- or hyperspectral bands as the predictor variables while the observed SOC and clay contents were considered as the target. The RF algorithm (Breiman 2001) was employed for calibration of the SOC and clay prediction models. Three RF parameters were defined before the modeling; i) quantity of forest trees (n_{tree}), ii) quantity of variables used for each tree (m_{try}), and the minimum data per node ($nodesize$) (Liaw et al., 2002). After a grid search within the range of 200 to 2000, 500 was found to be the optimal n_{tree} . The $nodesize$ of each terminal node was set to five, while m_{try} was decided to be one third of the total number of variables.

Table 1. Details of the indices and the related wavelengths used for each sensor

Index	Equation	L08-OLI band	S2 band	CASI/SASI	EnMAP	Reference
NDVI	$\frac{R_{NIR} - R_{red}}{R_{NIR} + R_{red}}$	R _{red} : 665 nm (B4) R _{NIR} : 865 nm (B5)	R _{red} : 665 nm (B4) R _{NIR} : 842 nm (B8)	R _{red} : 668.3 nm (B31) R _{NIR} : 848.9 nm (B50)	R _{red} : 666.64 nm (B48) R _{NIR} : 847.85 nm (B73)	Rouse et al., 1974
NBR2	$\frac{R_{SWIR1} - R_{SWIR2}}{R_{SWIR1} + R_{SWIR2}}$	R _{SWIR1} : 1610 nm (B6) R _{SWIR2} : 2200 nm (B7)	R _{SWIR1} : 1610 nm (B11) R _{SWIR2} : 2190 nm (B12)	R _{SWIR1} : 1602.5 nm (B106) R _{SWIR2} : 2202.5 nm (B146)	R _{SWIR1} : 1609.02 nm (B149) R _{SWIR2} : 2199.45 nm (B193)	(van Deventer et al., 1997)
nCAI	$\frac{0.5 \times (R_{2000} + R_{2200}) - R_{2100}}{0.5 \times (R_{2000} + R_{2200}) + R_{2100}}$	-	-	R ₂₀₀₀ : 2007.5 nm (B133) R ₂₁₀₀ : 2097.5 nm (B139) R ₂₂₀₀ : 2202.5 nm (B146)	R ₂₀₀₀ : 2005.8 nm (B80) R ₂₁₀₀ : 2104.59 nm (B91) R ₂₂₀₀ : 2199.45 nm (B102)	(Daughtry, 2001)

NBR2: Normalized Burn Ratio 2, NDVI: Normalized Differences Vegetation Index, nCAI: normalized Cellulose Absorption Index

2.8. Evaluation of the models

The mean error (ME), root mean square error (RMSE), coefficient of determination (R^2), Lin's concordance correlation coefficient (CCC) and ratio of performance to deviation (RPD) were used for assessment of the developed models on the testing dataset (Eq. 1 to 5).

$$ME = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (o_i - p_i)}{n} \quad (1)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (o_i - p_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (o_i - p_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (o_i - \mu_o)^2} \quad (3)$$

$$CCC = \frac{2\rho\sigma_o\sigma_p}{\sigma_o^2 + \sigma_p^2 + (\mu_o - \mu_p)^2} \quad (4)$$

$$RPD = \frac{\sigma_o}{RMSE} \quad (5)$$

where o_i and p_i are the observed and predicted values, μ_o and μ_p are the observed and predicted means, n is the number of samples, σ_o^2 and σ_p^2 are the observed and predicted variances and ρ is the Pearson correlation coefficient between the two variables. High R^2 , CCC and RPD and low ME and RMSE are generally expected.

2.9. Mapping of the SOC and clay

In addition to quantitative assessment of the developed models and the data used, the SOC and clay spatial distribution maps were constructed to perform a visual comparison. This was done by applying the SOC and clay constructed RF models to the related multi-, super- and hyperspectral data. The resulting spatial variability maps were compared to each other and to the one obtained after applying the most accurate prediction model to the related dataset. The general methodology of this study is summarized in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Summary of the methodology employed in this study

3. Results

3.1. Bare pixels selection

Table 2 shows the number of sample-pixels (n) covered by either green or dry vegetation, that have surpassed the related optimum thresholds (T) obtained for each of the indices and images. The table shows the number of common sample-pixels between the satellite and CS data with index values exceeding the related threshold (S).

Table 2. Details on the indices and the related optimum thresholds and sample-pixels for each of the sensors

Index		L08-OLI	S2	EnMAP	CS
NDVI	n	28	25	26	24
	T	0.20	0.21	0.21	0.23
	S	20	21	23	-
NBR2	n	8	7	7	6
	T	0.17	0.16	0.16	0.14
	S	4	4	5	-
nCAI	n	-	-	10	8
	T	-	-	-	-
	S	-	-	7	-

n: number of sample-pixels with index values surpassing T, T: threshold value, S: number of sample-pixels common with the CS data that have index values surpassing T

As evidenced in the table, the number of samples removed by applying the indices on the CS image pixels spectra was lower than the number of those removed by applying on the other sensors. The higher spatial resolution of the aerial image (CS), and hence the smaller pixels, led to less mixed pixels and better discrimination of cover types, which in turn resulted in less discarded samples. The number of samples considered as vegetation in EnMAP ($n = 26$ for NDVI and $n = 7$ for NBR2) and S2 ($n = 25$ for NDVI and $n = 7$ for NBR2) were closer to CS ($n = 24$ for NDVI and $n = 6$ for NBR2) than those of in L08-OLI ($n = 28$ for NDVI and $n = 8$ for NBR2). In addition, EnMAP had a higher number of common vegetation samples with CS (23 and 5 for NDVI and NBR2, respectively) than L08-OLI (20 and 4 for NDVI and NBR2, respectively) and S2 (21 and 4 for NDVI and NBR2, respectively). This could be explained by spectral resolution advantage of EnMAP over the multispectral satellite data. Comparing L08-OLI and S2, the better spatial resolution of S2 (10 m), which was closer to the spatial resolution of the CS image (2.5 m), can be a reason to justify its advantage over L08-OLI.

Comparing the performance of the NBR2 and nCAI indices on the hyperspectral data, less sample-pixels were considered as dry vegetation by the NBR2. This might be attributed to the moisture acting as a disturbing factor on NBR2, obscuring the effects of dry vegetation. Furthermore, the common samples between EnMAP and CS recognized by the nCAI were 7, which is more than those obtained by the NBR2 (5). These advantages of nCAI over NBR2 might be due to the fact that nCAI index exclusively covers 2000, 2100 and 2200 nm wavelengths specific to some dry vegetation structural compounds such as lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose (Daughtry et al., 1996).

Finally, samples which surpassed the related threshold values were discarded from the modeling process. In addition, samples identified as inclusive outliers for each image were excluded from the modeling procedure on all other sensors to retrieve similar number of remaining bare soil samples (78) fully compatible between all datasets. For mapping purpose, models were applied on the bare soil pixels retrieved only using NDVI and NBR2 indices.

3.2. General statistics

General statistics of the SOC and clay contents of the remaining bare soil samples are presented in Table 3. Accordingly, the SOC content ranged between 0.31 and 2.01% with the average of 1.09%, while the clay content varied within the range of 6.77 and 26.25% with average of 13.77%. The SOC levels differed between the study sites ranging between 0.69 to

1.19% and 0.31 to 2.01% with the mean values of 0.93 and 1.11% for Jičín and Přestavlky, respectively. The clay content also varied between 15.46 to 23.42% and 6.77 to 26.25% with averages of 18.29 and 12.36% for Jičín and Přestavlky, respectively. Both SOC and clay showed positive skewness for both sites, with the largest values of 0.54 and 1.18, respectively. Considering the coefficient of variation (CV), clay showed higher variability than SOC indicating a more heterogeneous distribution.

Table 3 Summary statistics of SOC and clay content (%) of the samples

Study site	n	Parameter	Min	Max	Mean	StD	CV	Skewness
Jičín	17	SOC	0.69	1.19	0.93	0.15	0.16	0.45
		Clay	15.46	23.42	18.29	2.50	0.14	0.72
Přestavlky	61	SOC	0.31	2.01	1.11	0.26	0.23	0.54
		Clay	6.77	26.25	12.36	3.78	0.30	1.18
All	78	SOC	0.31	2.01	1.09	0.29	0.24	0.59
		Clay	6.77	26.25	13.77	4.31	0.31	0.59

n: number of samples, Min: minimum, Max: maximum, StD: standard deviation, CV: coefficient of variation

3.3. Comparing the spectra

A preliminary visual comparison between the selected sample-pixels' spectra of different sensors is presented in Fig. 4. Pixels were from different surface cover types of bare soil, green vegetation, and dry vegetation. As evidenced, the overall trends of the spectra were similar for all spectral data types. In addition, the reflectance and absorption peaks were in relatively the same wavelengths, even though, many extrema and details in the spectra of CS and EnMAP were not present in S2 and L08-OLI spectra.

Table 4 shows the NDVI, NBR2 and nCAI indices values calculated for the bare soil, green and dry vegetation sample-pixels from each sensor. Accordingly, no big difference was observed in the values of each individual index between the satellites and CS data, which suggested that there were not significant variations between the soil spectral properties retrieved from different sensors.

Fig. 4. Representative sample-pixels' spectra derived from different sensors: a) bare soil (in Přestavky), b) green vegetation (in Jičín), and c) dry vegetation (in Přestavky)

Table 4. Spectral indices calculated for representative sample-pixels in each image

Sample-pixel surface cover type	Index	L08-OLI	S2	EnMAP	CS
Bare soil	NDVI	0.16	0.11	0.14	0.13
	NBR2	0.10	0.09	0.04	0.06
	nCAI	-	-	< 0.001	< 0.001
Green vegetation	NDVI	0.26	0.23	0.36	0.32
	NBR2	0.03	0.06	0.07	0.07
	nCAI	-	-	< 0.001	< 0.001
Dry vegetation	NDVI	0.17	0.13	0.11	0.12
	NBR2	0.20	0.21	0.17	0.15
	nCAI	-	-	~ 0.002	~ 0.002

According to the calculated SAM values (Table 5), there were various degrees of similarity between the satellite and airborne images samples-pixels spectra. The spectral similarity was higher in Vis–NIR compared to SWIR, which can be due to the higher spectral resolution of all sensors in the Vis–NIR region. Furthermore, EnMAP showed the highest similarity with the CS image spectra while the lowest similarity was obtained from L08-OLI.

Table 5: Spectral similarity between L08-OLI, S2 and EnMAP spectra and CS spectra calculated by SAM method

Sample	L08-OLI	S2	EnMAP
Vis–NIR	0.09	0.07	0.06
SWIR	0.25	0.23	0.19

SAM threshold value of 0.3, which has been successfully used by Galal et al. (2012) and Khosravi et al. (2022), was also considered in this study to recognize the similarity and dissimilarity between the two spectra. As evidenced in the table, all SAM outputs were lower than that threshold value ($SAM < 0.3$). This indicated enough proximity between different types of images' spectra and hence prediction models developed on those spectra are comparable.

3.4. Modeling results

Table 6 displays the SOC and clay prediction performance of the RF models developed on L08-OLI, S2, EnMAP and CS data. It can be seen that the SOC and clay models developed on EnMAP data outperformed those developed on L08-OLI and S2 images, while underperformed by those developed on the CS data. Furthermore, the prediction of SOC using EnMAP was moderate for both study sites separately and together ($RPD \geq 1.35$, $R^2 \geq 0.56$, $RMSE \leq 0.19\%$). Clay was fairly predicted with higher statistical accuracy than SOC for both sites, separately and together ($RPD \geq 1.55$, $R^2 \geq 0.69$ and $RMSE \leq 2.45\%$). The best SOC and clay predictions were obtained for Přestavlky, while the lowest accuracies of both parameters were seen in Jičín.

Table 6. Performance of SOC and clay prediction models developed on EnMAP and other sensors' spectra (validation data)

Site		Landsat 8-OLI					Sentinel-2					EnMAP					CASI/SASI				
		ME	RMSE	R ²	CCC	RPD	ME	RMSE	R ²	CCC	RPD	ME	RMSE	R ²	CCC	RPD	ME	RMSE	R ²	CCC	RPD
Jičín (17 samples)	SOC	0.09	0.21	0.39	0.42	0.71	-0.12	0.17	0.49	0.55	0.83	0.08	0.11	0.56	0.63	1.39	0.07	0.10	0.65	0.70	1.53
	Clay	-0.48	3.74	0.58	0.60	0.67	0.35	3.25	0.61	0.65	0.77	-0.28	1.61	0.69	0.69	1.55	-0.22	1.46	0.76	0.78	1.71
Přestavlky (61 samples)	SOC	-0.11	0.22	0.53	0.56	1.18	-0.19	0.15	0.59	0.67	1.73	0.08	0.12	0.64	0.71	2.19	0.03	0.10	0.71	0.71	2.62
	Clay	0.79	2.95	0.65	0.69	1.28	-0.13	2.32	0.70	0.72	1.63	0.17	1.68	0.76	0.83	2.25	-0.24	1.43	0.81	0.85	2.65
All (78 samples)	SOC	0.09	0.26	0.47	0.51	1.11	-0.14	0.23	0.57	0.59	1.26	0.05	0.19	0.61	0.66	1.35	-0.03	0.12	0.67	0.73	1.81
	Clay	-0.66	2.65	0.58	0.63	1.63	-0.41	2.51	0.66	0.68	1.72	0.26	2.45	0.71	0.75	1.76	0.29	1.70	0.79	0.85	2.54

The differences between the performance of models developed on EnMAP and those developed on the L08-OLI and S2 datasets were more evident for SOC quantification. Accordingly, compared to L08-OLI, average RMSE and R^2 improvements of 40% and 31% were observed for the models developed on EnMAP (considering both areas separated and together). That was while the average improvements were 28% and 12% compared to when the S2 data were used. Estimation of clay by EnMAP showed less average enhancement of 36% and 27% for RMSE and 19% and 10% for R^2 compared to using L08-OLI and S2, respectively. On the other hand, the models developed on EnMAP showed lower performance compared to those constructed on the CS data, especially for SOC, where the average RMSE and R^2 inferiority of 21% and 12% were observed on accuracy of the models developed on the EnMAP data. Estimation results of clay by EnMAP showed less average difference (18% for RMSE and 9% for R^2) from those obtained by the CS.

Although fewer samples were used, the EnMAP models developed for Přestavlky site yielded better performance than those developed on both study sites together (RMSE and R^2 superiority of 37% and 5% for SOC and 31% and 7% for clay, respectively). The complex relationship between both sites' samples complicated capturing of a proper trend between the predictor and response variables, compared to when only one site samples were considered.

3.5. Variable importance

Fig. 5 shows the top 20 influential variables of the models developed on all samples as well as their relative increase in mean squared error in percentage (%IncMSE) as the variable importance criteria. Accordingly, the top selected bands of EnMAP were relatively similar to those of CS in terms of the spectral range the bands belonged to. Considering the SOC-related results, at least three out of the top five important variables of each image were in the visible range (525.69, 411.58 and 658.8 for CS and 571.76, 660.21, and 520.55 For EnMAP). Most of the 20 selected bands also belonged to the visible range (10 for EnMAP and 13 for CS). Regarding clay, the most important contributing variables for both hyperspectral datasets were extracted from the SWIR region with 12 and 14 bands for EnMAP and CS, respectively (Fig. 5). These results showed that EnMAP shared a fairly similar mechanism with CS on prediction of the SOC and clay. Such as EnMAP and CS, similar spectral regions were found to be important for L08-OLI and S2 sensors, in a way that their top importance bands for SOC

and clay predictions were from the visible and SWIR regions, respectively. Accordingly, for SOC, the L08-OLI band 3 (530–590 nm) and S2 band 4 (650–680 nm) were the most influential variables, while for clay the L08-OLI band 7 (2110–2290 nm) and S2 band 12 (2100–2280 nm) had the highest importance level.

Fig. 5. Variable importance plots for SOC (a-d) and clay (f-h) prediction models for both study sites' samples together (%IncMSE: increase in mean squared error in percentage)

3.6. Spatial distribution maps

The developed models were used to create the 10 m resolution SOC and clay spatial distribution maps (Figs. 6 and 7). The maps provided using EnMAP, L08-OLI and S2 were compared to those constructed on the CS data as the one yielded the most accurate prediction results (Table 6). Generally, maps constructed on EnMAP presented similar spatial distribution trends with those developed on the CS data. The low and medium SOC content areas were fairly localized in both Jičín and Přestavlky (Fig. 6). Regarding clay, the high content areas were well differentiated for the study sites, showing relatively similar hotspot trends between EnMAP and CS (Fig. 7).

Considering the individual study sites, EnMAP properly mapped the low to medium SOC contents on the eastern and western parts of Jičín. The middle and southern parts illustrated relatively higher SOC contents. Regarding Přestavlky, using EnMAP data, SOC was predicted to be higher in the middle and northeastern parts, while the western and southwestern areas were estimated to contain lower SOC contents. Despite general trend similarities with CS, the upper limits of SOC contents predicted by EnMAP were higher than real values. For the clay maps (Fig. 7), EnMAP appropriately delineated the higher clay levels in the southwestern parts of Jičín and middle parts of Přestavlky.

Compared to L08-OLI and S2, EnMAP was more successful in estimation of the SOC and clay distributions, presenting higher similarity to the CS map. Although the general spatial trend predicted by L08-OLI, with lower spectral and spatial resolution, was relatively similar to CS (except for Jičín/SOC), the range of the predicted parameters and hence the hotspots did not coincide well. It might be due to the fact that the higher values could not be properly predicted by L08-OLI, especially in those parts with predominant low SOC and clay contents. Compared to L08-OLI, the maps based on S2 could better highlight the areas with high level values of SOC and clay. This superiority can be mainly due to the better spatial resolution of S2, particularly within the Vis–NIR region. In addition, the parts with lower SOC values as well as those with medium clay contents exhibited a similar pattern with the maps produced based on CS. The same mapping behavior using S2 data has also been reported by Gholizadeh et al. (2018) and Žížala et al. (2019).

Fig. 6. Spatial distribution maps of SOC for Jičín (first row) and Přebavky (second row) areas obtained using L08-OLI, S2, EnMAP, and CS (first to fourth columns, respectively).

Fig.7. Spatial distribution maps of clay for Jičín (first row) and Přebavky (second row) areas obtained using L08-OLI, S2, EnMAP, and CS (first to fourth columns respectively).

4. Discussion

As outlined in section 3.4, predictions obtained by EnMAP models were less accurate than outputs of the CS ones. One of the main reasons is the lower spatial resolution of the spaceborne sensor. The lower spatial resolution increases the risk of sample-pixels with mixed spectra. In addition, the larger distance to the imaging target and consequent atmospheric effects as well as the higher spectral resolution of EnMAP has led to lower SNR and prediction performance than CS. Compared to SOC, the difference between performance of the two hyperspectral datasets was less prominent for clay. One explanation can be the presence of enough EnMAP bands within the SWIR region and the clay related key spectral features are being specifically covered (Castaldi et al., 2016). In a study on the impact of spectral configurations simulated from airborne-based AISA-DUAL hyperspectral data on estimation and mapping of clay content (Gomez et al., 2018), EnMAP simulated sensor with regular spectral resolutions from 5 to 100 nm provided high prediction performances ($R^2_{\text{val}} = 0.78$ and $\text{RPD} = 2.18$), even better than those obtained by the AISA-DUAL ($R^2_{\text{val}} = 0.77$ and $\text{RPD} = 2.14$).

The better accuracy of EnMAP compared to the L08-OLI and S2 was primarily attributed to the higher spectral resolution of the hyperspectral data (more than 200 bands with narrow bandwidths) and hence incorporation of more SOC and clay related key wavelengths which may not show up in the lower spectral resolution data, especially those acquired by the multispectral satellite sensors like L08-OLI. This was despite the unavoidable decrease in SNR which can offset the value of high spectral resolution, especially within the SWIR range which contains some of the key soil spectral features (Lobell and Asner, 2002). The significant improvements in recently launched or upcoming hyperspectral sensors, as compared to the old generation of imagers such as Hyperion, will avoid deterioration of SNR specifically in the SWIR region (Castaldi et al., 2016).

SOC content has shown correlations with visible range 410, 520, 570, and 660 nm wavelengths (Daniel et al. 2004; Viscarra Rossel et al., 2006). Furthermore, strong correlations have reportedly been observed between organic matter (OM) (including SOC) and reflectance in the NIR and SWIR ranges (Henderson et al., 1992; Ladoni et al., 2010). Accordingly, several OM related wavelengths have been recognized thus far, such as: 960 nm, 1100 nm, 1720 nm, 1744 nm, 1870 nm and 2052 nm, 2180 nm and 2309 nm (Dalal and Henry 1986; Sudduth and Hummel, 1991; Shepherd and Walsh 2002; Daniel et al. 2004). Considering Fig. 5, most of the

important variables of EnMAP were in accordance with those introduced as SOC-related key spectral wavelengths. As three top contributing wavelengths, 520, 570 nm, and 660 nm are separately covered by the EnMAP B22 (517.54 to 523.56 nm), B32 (568.46 to 575.05 nm), and B47 (656.40 to 666.02 nm). Besides, the EnMAP important wavelengths obtained for prediction of SOC were relatively similar to those yielded for the CS data so that from all the 20 important wavelengths detected, 12 were close between the two types of hyperspectral data (Fig. 5). On the other hand, L08-OLI and S2 sensors cover a limited number of specific wavelengths by their nonspecific broad bands and only 2 of the key features in the visible range were between the first 3 important variables of the two multi- and superspectral satellite data (Band 3 for L08-OLI and Band 4 for S2).

There are three main active spectral features for clay minerals: (i) 1300-1400 nm (overtone by hydroxyl (OH)), (ii) 1800-1900 nm (overtone by molecular water), and (iii) 2200-2500 nm (combination tones by Aluminum hydroxide (Al-OH) and Iron hydroxide (Fe-OH) and/or Magnesium hydroxide (Mg-OH) (Ben-Dor et al., 1999; Fang et al., 2018). Chlorite features a weak absorption peak at around 1400 nm and two at 2250 and 2350 nm related to Fe-OH and Mg-OH, respectively (Fang et al., 2018). Kaolinite has two double spectral features of 1390 and 1410 nm and 2160 and 2210 nm (Fang et al., 2018). Montmorillonite and Illite exhibit three main absorption peaks at approximately 1400, 1900, and 2200 nm. Montmorillonite is also characterized by the weak shoulders about 1468 nm and 1970 nm, while illite shows two Al-OH related features at around 2344 and 2445 nm (Clark et al., 1990). Similar to SOC, most of the above-mentioned wavelengths are covered by narrow bands EnMAP data and also were in the list of important variables shown in Fig. 5. As example, the influential 2200 nm, 2250 nm and 2300 nm wavelengths are included in EnMAP B102 (2195.40 to 2203.50 nm), B108 (2245.45 to 2253.35 nm), and B114 (2294.30 to 2302.03 nm), within the SWIR region, as well as the list of important variables for EnMAP dataset. Nonetheless, only a few of the clay key wavelengths are under the coverage of the broad band L08-OLI and S2 datasets. In addition, of all those few key features, only one band of L08-OLI (Band 7) and S2 (Bands 12) was among the top 3 in the list of important variables. Of above-mentioned wavelengths, 2300 nm is not covered by any of the L08-OLI and S2 bands while the 2200 nm and 2250 nm are jointly included in the L08-OLI B7 and S2 B12.

Within the realm of the space-borne platforms, superiority of hyperspectral sensors over multi- or superspectral ones in prediction of SOC and/or clay has been occasionally documented. In an investigation on the impact of SNR and spectral resolution on prediction of some soil parameters including SOC and clay (Castaldi et al., 2016), PLSR models constructed on resampled and simulated EnMAP data performed relatively better than those developed on L08-OLI and S2 data. Gomez et al. (2018) proved the superiority of PLSR models built on simulated EnMAP over those calibrated on L08-OLI and S2. Mzid et al. (2022) conducted a local scale study to compare capability of the PRISMA sensor with S2 and L8-OLI on prediction and mapping of SOC and soil texture. Their results were in favor of hyperspectral data with higher prediction accuracies.

In spite of the above-mentioned reports, some models developed on S2 yielded high accuracies near to those built on simulated EnMAP. Compared to the narrow-band hyperspectral imagers, the broad-band S2 collects higher levels of electromagnetic energy, leading to acquisition of the higher SNR data. This partly reimburses the lower spectral resolution of the S2 sensor and hence increases its prediction accuracy. Castaldi et al. (2016) reported successful quantification of SOC and clay by simulated S2, comparable to some other simulated hyperspectral data (including EnMAP). Similarly, in a study on estimation of SOC and clay by Gholizadeh et al. (2018), satisfactory SOC and clay estimations were yielded by models constructed on the S2 images, comparable to those resulted from the CS hyperspectral data.

As the final highlight, higher spectral and spatial resolution (especially in Vis–NIR regions) of the Copernicus sensor, brought about higher prediction accuracies, than L08-OLI, for both of the soil properties, compatible to what has previously been reported by Castaldi, (2021) and Mzid et al. (2022). This advantage of S2 over L08-OLI was more evident on quantification of SOC, which can be due to the high quality of S2 in Vis–NIR regions, where the majority of SOC related key spectral wavelengths reside (Mzid et al., 2022).

5. Conclusions

nCAI index was more successful in discrimination of the dry vegetation and as such the bare soil pixels, compared to the well-known NBR2 which is usually influenced by the moisture disturbances. SOC prediction results on EnMAP were relatively comparable to those obtained

by the higher spatial resolution CS data. In addition, EnMAP-based models were superior to those constructed on L08-OLI and S2 for both soil parameters in the study sites. Difference in the spectral and spatial resolution of data types was the main reason for dissimilar performances of the models. Considering the spatial distribution maps, similar trends were observed between the EnMAP and CS and it properly determined the low and medium SOC content in the studied sites. The parts with elevated levels of clay were also appropriately mapped in both sites. As a general conclusion, EnMAP presented high capability in prediction and mapping of SOC and clay contents in local scale agricultural lands. Compared to the aerial hyperspectral sensor, the inherent limitations such as relatively weak SNR and low spatial resolution can be compensated by the EnMAP's large spatial coverage and frequent revisit-time. The expected release of more scenes will facilitate further in-depth investigations on how to deal with above-mentioned shortcomings associated with the new hyperspectral sensor's data.

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Appendix

Table S1. Study sites and image acquisition dates

Site	Landsat-8 image acquisition date	Sentinel-2 image acquisition date	EnMAP image acquisition date	Airborne image acquisition date
Jičín	03.10.2023	02.10.2023	02.10.2023	03.06.2021
Přestavlky	03.10.2023	02.10.2023	10.10.2023	03.06.2021

Table S2. L08-OLI bands specifications

Band	Band description	Wavelength range (nm)	Central wavelength (nm)	Spatial resolution (m)
Band 1	Coastal Aerosol	430-450	440	30
Band 2	Blue	450-510	480	30
Band 3	Green	530-590	560	30
Band 4	Red	640-670	655	30
Band 5	NIR	850-880	865	30
Band 6	SWIR 1	1570-1650	1610	30
Band 7	SWIR 2	2110-2290	2200	30
Band 8	PAN	500-680	590	15
Band 9	Cirrus	1360-1380	1370	30

nm: nanometers, NIR: near infrared, SWIR: shortwave infrared, PAN: Panchromatic

Table S3. S2 bands specifications

Band	Band description	Wavelength range (nm)	Central wavelength (nm)	Spatial resolution (m)
Band 1	Coastal Aerosol	433-453	443	60
Band 2	Blue	458-523	490	10
Band 3	Green	543-578	560	10
Band 4	Red	650-680	665	10
Band 5	Vegetation red edge	698-713	705	20
Band 6	Vegetation red edge	733-748	740	20
Band 7	Vegetation red edge	773-793	783	20
Band 8	NIR	785-900	842	10
Band 8A	Vegetation red edge	855-875	865	20
Band 9	Water vapor	935-955	940	60
Band 10	SWIR - Cirrus	1360-1390	1375	60
Band 11	SWIR	1565-1655	1610	20
Band 12	SWIR	2100-2280	2190	20

nm: nanometers, NIR: near infrared, SWIR: shortwave infrared

Table S4. EnMAP bands specifications

Spectral region	Number of bands	Spectral range (nm)	Mean spectral sampling distance (nm)	Spatial resolution (m)	Radiometric resolution (bit)	Swath width (km)
Vis-NIR	91	420-1000	6.5	30	14	30
SWIR	133	900-2450	10			

Table S5. CASI and SASI sensors details

Sensor	Number of bands	Spectral range (nm)	Spectral resolution (nm)	Field of view (FOV)	FWHM (nm)
CASI	72	Vis–NIR, 380–1050	3.2	40°	10
SASI	100	SWIR, 950–2450	15	40°	15

FWHM: Full Width at Half Maximum

Highlights

- First study exploring the use of EnMAP data on prediction and mapping of SOC and clay.
- nCAI index was more successful in discrimination of the dry vegetation and bare soil pixels, compared to the well-known NBR2.
- EnMAP-based models properly determined the low and medium SOC content and elevated levels of clay.
- EnMAP-based models were superior to those constructed on L08-OLI and S2.
- The expected release of more EnMAP data will facilitate further in-depth investigations.